

Studies on the effect of pebrine disease on *Daba T.V.* of *Antheraea mylitta* Drury

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ABSTRACT

An attempt was made to evaluate the impact of *Nosema species* on *Daba T.V.* in respect of transovarial transmitted (observed as T₁), secondarily infected (observed as T₂) and Healthy silkworm (observed as T₃). The larval and pupa mortality was 40 and 12% in T₁, 30 and 8% in T₂ and in case of T₃ there was no mortality. In comparison to the control, significant impact of infection on larval weight, Number of moths emerged, fecundity, hatching percent, cocoon weight, shell weight, filament length, reelability, weight of the silk reeled was observed. There is no significant variation between T₁ and T₂ groups.

Key words : Pebrine, *Antheraea mylitta*, *Daba T.V.*

Antheraea mylitta D (*Daba T.V.*) a sericigenous endemic species of the India is often infected with an intracellular parasite of the genus *Nosema*. Pebrine can be acquired from the mother moth (primary infection) or from the environment through food (secondary infection). Infected larvae show black pepper like spots on the integument. These are the infected hypodermal cells become enlarged and vacuolated get blackened due to the formation of melanin (Ganga, 2003). Larvae infected with *Nosema* sp. show extended development period, reduced size and larval weight in comparison to uninfected ones (Rath *et al.* 2003). The infected larvae of *Bombyx mori* show significant changes in the cocoon weight, shell weight, denier, reelability etc., (Bhat and Nataraju, 2005). Several strains and species of microsporidia have since been isolated from silkworms and other insects (Kishore, *et al.* 1994; Bhat and Nataraju, 2004). Chakrabarti and Manna (2006) identified three *Nosema* spp. from three non-mulberry silkworms as *Nosema mylitta* from *Antheraea mylitta*, *N. ricini* from *Philosamia ricini* and *N. assamensis* from *A. assamensis*. Some of the microsporidia show transovarial transmission and some are not (Fujiware, 1980; Fujiware, 1984; Ananthalakshmi *et al.* 1994; Nageshwara Rao, *et al.* 2004). Most of the species are highly virulent and

mortality caused by them also varies. No silkworm race reported to be completely immune to *pebrine*. Spores of *Nosema* sp. can be detected at any stage of life cycle in *Tasar* silkworm (Sharan, *et al.* 1992) and are different in size, shape and pathogenicity (Bhat, *et al.* 2009). Present study was under taken to observe effect of *pebrine* on *Daba T.V.* of *Antheraea mylitta*.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The present work was done at Basic seed multiplication and Training centre, Central silk board, Chennai, Adilabad District, Andhra Pradesh, India, by collecting the *Daba T.V.* cocoons during the month of June. The cocoons were preserved in the cages made up of wire mesh of size 2 × 2 × 2 under suitable temperature and humidity. The emerged moths were tested for *pebrine* disease by a method derived from that used in sericulture (Pasteur, 1870). The abdomen of an adult was severed with scissors and placed in a small mortar, mixed with water and crushed with pestle. A drop of the smear was placed on a clean slide and examined under a microscope of 600 × magnification for *Nosema* sp., spores. The eggs from healthy and infected moths were prepared and incubated.

Isolation of microsporidian spores : Microsporidian spores were isolated from diseased larvae of *Daba T.V.* homogenized in 0.6% K₂CO₃, filtered and the

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filtrate was centrifuged at 3000 rpm for 15 min to sediment the spores. The supernatant was discarded. The sediment was suspended in 1 ml distilled water and mixed with percoll (poly vinyl silica particles) and centrifuged at 5000 rpm for 15 min. The spores were collected from the sediment and washed in distilled water thrice and stored as stock at 4°C in 0.85% Na Cl until use. The spores were suspended in distilled water and spore count was enumerated by Neubauer haemocytometer. The stock solution was diluted to obtain an inoculum dosage of 1×10^7 spores/ml. Healthy third instar larvae were starved for 3-4 h to induce hunger and then fed on the *Terminalia arjuna* leaves smeared with inoculum dosage.

Effect of the microsporidian parasite infection on the larval weight, survival and commercial characters of *Daba T.V.* : First instar larvae were subjected to following three treatments

1. Transovarian infection-T₁
2. Secondary infection-T₂
3. Healthy worms (Control)-T₃

Larvae hatched from the eggs laid by the infected moths were kept as T₁. Larvae fed on the leaves treated with the microsporidian spores of 1×10^7 spores/ml were kept as T₂. Larvae hatched from the eggs laid by the healthy *Daba T.V.* moth were kept as T₃. The three treatments were brushed and reared separately on freshly cut *Terminalia arjuna* leaves in the laboratory. Each treatment had five replications of 50 larvae and reared till cocoonig following standard procedure. Larval weight, Larval mortality, Pupa mortality Moth emergence, Hatchability percent were recorded for all the three treatments. Commercial characters for treatments T₁, T₂, T₃ were also recorded. Larvae that were died because of Pebrine were examined for the presence of spores under light microscope everyday till spinning and included for data analysis. Many spores of oval shape were identified. Larvae that were died due to other reasons were excluded from the statistical analysis.

Statistical analysis : To estimate the effect of pebrine disease one way ANOVA was used for the three groups T₁, T₂ and T₃. One concerned approach is whether there would be equal performance in the three groups. Critical differences (CD 5%) was analysed by Tukeys post hoc procedure. All the three groups were compared with each other to find the resultant difference between the groups which

explains whether there is a significant variation between the groups on correlation with CD 5%. All the data presented were the average values of five replications.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The larval weight in case of transovarian infection was 23.08 gm while that of T₂ and T₃ batch was 26.13 and 32.18 gms respectively. Mortality rate of the larvae and pupa found be 40 and 12% in T₁ batch due to transovarian transmission and 30 and 8% in T₂ batch due to secondary infection. In T₁ and T₂ batches 48 and 62% larvae survived to form cocoons while incase of T₃ batch 96% larvae were survived to form cocoons. There was 78.87% infection found in moths emerged from transovarian infection and in case of secondarily infection 61.64% of the moths emerged found to be infected. Fecundity found to be 179 in case of the moths emerged from T₃ batch and it was 88 in case of moths emerged from T₁ batch. The infected layings were found to be 83.13% in T₁ batch and 66.71% in T₂ batch. Hatchability was found to be at the top in case of eggs laid by healthy moths (72%).When compared with the T₃ batch hatchability found to be negligible in T₁ batch (29%) and in T₂ batch it was low (48%).

Table 2 shows the results of cocoon characters. The single cocoon weight of T₁ batch was 6.02 gm while that of T₂ and T₃ batch were 7.04, 9.38 gm respectively. There was a significant decrease in the weight of T₁ and T₂ batch cocoons. The shell weight of the cocoon in T₁ batch was 0.79 gms while that of T₂ and T₃ batch was 0.86 and 1.02 gm respectively. It is observed that the shell weight of T₁ batch cocoons has not varied much from that of T₂ batch. It is observed that the shell ratio (SR%) was high (12.62%) in case of cocoons obtained from transovarian infection whereas least was observed in healthy batch. The filament length of T₁ batch cocoon was 109.4 m, whereas T₂ and T₃ batch cocoons have shown 145.23 and 266.27 m respectively. It is evident from the results that the filament length has seriously affected by the transovarian mode of infection. The filament length of the T₂ batch cocoon has decreased by 54.54% when compared with T₃. The denier of T₁ batch cocoon was 17.27, while that of T₂ and T₃ batch cocoons were 16.73 and 13.18 respectively. The denier found to be less in T₃ batch. A significant increase in the denier values of T₁ and T₂ batches were noticed which can be attributed to

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pebrine. In case of pupal mortality, since all three comparisons result in a difference greater than CD 5%, the three groups differ significantly. The previous reports of Bhat, *et al.* (2009) on *Bombyx mori* have shown maximum mortality of silkworm larvae during early stages than fourth and fifth instars infected by *Nosema sp.* In comparison with the control the percentage larvae survived to form cocoons was too low in transovarian infection than in secondary infection.

The comparison for Number of moths emerged and percentage of infected moths between the groups explains that T_1 and T_2 do not differ significantly whereas T_1 and T_3 , T_2 and T_3 differ significantly because of pebrine only 88 eggs were laid by the moths of T_1 batch whereas the number of eggs laid by the T_2 batch moths was 40% less than the T_3 batch and the percentage of infected layings were also high in T_1 and T_2 batch. The comparison for fecundity between the groups explains that T_1 and T_2 do not differ significantly whereas T_1 and T_3 , T_2 and T_3 differ significantly because of pebrine. The decline in ovary weight, fecundity, and fertility in *A. mylitta* larvae infected with *Nosema sp.* was reported by Rath *et al.* (2003). The high spore concentration of *Nosema* in the gonads of *A. mylitta*, *A. assamensis* and *B. mori* will effect the reproductive potential and fertility. Significant variation in the hatchability was noticed among T_1 , T_2 and T_3 batches.

It is evident that the commercial characters were poor in case of the cocoons obtained from transovarian transmission (T_1) whereas the cocoons from secondary infection (T_2) have shown medium results. Cocoon weight and shell weight in T_1 and T_2 batches were recorded less than the T_3 batch and in T_1 batch it was less by 36 and 23%. In case of cocoon weight and shell weight, since all three comparisons result in a difference greater than CD 5%, the three groups differ significantly. Rath *et al.* (2003) have reported the decrease in shell weight in *A. mylitta* larvae infected with *Nosema sp.* Rath, *et al.* (2003) working on parasitization of fifth instar larvae of *A. mylitta* by *Uzifly* have reported the decrease (27-63.5%) in cocoon weight and shell weight in the infected larvae.

The filament length in T_1 batch was recorded least and it was 59% less than the control. The filament length of T_2 batch was 45.5% less than T_3

batch. The comparison for filament length between the groups explains that T_1 and T_2 do not differ significantly whereas T_1 and T_3 , T_2 and T_3 differ significantly because of pebrine Highest denier can be attributed to T_1 batch and least denier to T_3 batch. Thus the silk quality seems to be reduced due to the infection. According to Bhat, *et al.* (2009) silk from the cocoons of infected larvae is usually much inferior.

The reelability also reduced in case of infection and it was almost 46.2% less in T_1 batch cocoons than T_3 batch. The reeled silk weight from single cocoon was also reduced a lot in case of infection rather than the healthy cocoons. In case of denier, reelability and weight of the silk reeled, since all three comparisons result in a difference greater than CD 5%, the three groups differ significantly. Rath *et al.* (2003) have reported the decrease in silk gland weight in *A. mylitta* larvae infected with *Nosema sp.* which finally reduces the silk production.

Studies revealed that the impact of microsporidian parasite infection on commercial characters of *Daba T.V.* was high through transovarial infection rather than secondarily infected. A control over the secondary infection will reduce the damage caused and also increases the yield qualitatively and quantitatively.

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Table 1. Effect of pebrine disease on the larval weight, survival, fecundity and hatching of *Anthereae mylitta D* (*Daba T.V.*) (First crop).

Treatment	Larval weight (gm)	Larval mortality (No.)	Pupa mortality (No.)	No. of moths emerged	% of infected moths	No. of eggs laid	% of infected layings	Hatching (%)
T ₁	23.08	20	6	24	78.87	88	83.13	29
T ₂	26.13	15	4	31	61.64	107	66.71	48
T ₃	32.18	0	0	48	0	179	0	72
CD 5%	-	0.18	0.16	0.2	0.16	47	-	-
Difference of Means of								
T ₁ and T ₂	-	0.1	0.18	0.14	0.16	19	-	-
T ₁ and T ₃		0.4	0.12	0.48	0.78	91		
T ₂ and T ₃		0.3	0.3	0.34	0.62	72		

CD= Critical difference. All the values are the average values of five replications.

Table 2. Impact of pebrine disease on the commercial characters of *Anthereae mylitta D* (*Daba T.V.*) (First crop).

Treatment	Single cocoon weight (gm)	Single shell weight (gm)	SR%	Single cocoon filament length (mtrs)	Denier	Reelability (%)	Weight of silk reeled from single cocoon (gm)
T ₁	6.02	0.79	12.62	109.4	17.27	34.88	0.21
T ₂	7.04	0.86	12.21	145.23	16.73	38.35	0.27
T ₃	9.38	1.02	10.87	266.27	13.18	41.57	0.39
CD 5%	0.13	0.02	-	86.52	0.39	0.16	0.012
Difference of Means of							
T ₁ and T ₂	1.02	0.07	-	36	0.83	0.30	0.055
T ₁ and T ₃	3.36	0.22		157	4.28	1.2	0.18
T ₂ and T ₃	2.33	0.16		121	3.45	0.89	0.12

CD= Critical difference. All the values are the average values of five replications.

the serious impact of microsporidian infection. The reelability of T₁ batch cocoon was 34.88%, while that in T₂ and T₃ batches were 38.35 and 41.57% respectively. There was a significant difference in the reelability of infected and healthy cocoons. The weight of the silk reeled of T₁ batch cocoon was 0.21 gm, whereas in T₂ and T₃ batch cocoons they were 0.27, 0.39 gm respectively. It is evident from the results that the reeled silk weight in T₃ batch cocoons was more than 46.2 and 30.8% from T₂ and T₁ batch cocoons.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The virulence due to microsporidian isolate from *Daba T.V.* was very high and had much impact on various characters of the ecorace. The findings of

Ramadevi, *et al.* (2010) working on pathological effects of microsporidian isolate from teak defoliator have observed 88.7% of transovarial transmission. In case of Transovarian infection the larval weight found to be less than 28.3% when compared to control. The decrease in food consumption, digestion, relative consumption rate, efficiency of conversion of ingested food in fifth instar of *A. mylitta* infected with *Nosema sp.* reduced the relative growth rate of the larvae (Rath *et al.* 2003).

The mortality rate of the larvae and pupa in transovarial infection (T₁) was high when compared to secondary infection (T₂). The comparison for larval mortality between the groups explains that T₁ and T₂ do not differ significantly whereas T₁ and T₃, T₂ and T₃ differ significantly because of